

EFFECT OF GRAPHITIZATION OF CARBON FIBER ON TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF YOUNG'S MODULUS OF C/C COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

As one of the most important basic mechanical properties of advanced C/C composites for high temperature structural applications, temperature dependences of Young's modulus were precisely studied in a vacuum with a lateral vibration method from room temperature up to 1373 K. Materials used were two kinds of unidirectional C/C composites, where the variables were microstructure of carbon fibers in C/C composites and heat treatment temperature of C/C composites. The temperature dependences of Young's modulus showed positive and negative trends reflecting microstructure changes of carbon fibers by heat treatments. Also, the graphitization effects of carbon fibers on the temperature dependences are presented quantitatively.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon composites (C/C composites) are the most promising materials for high temperature structural applications, such as high heat flux component for fusion reactors and thermal protection structures for space planes [1,2], where temperature dependence of mechanical properties are of interest. As an important part of design database, elastic properties of C/C composites have to be measured and quantitatively evaluated. The authors have pointed out the importance of the characteristic features that there has been positive and negative dependences of Young's modulus on test temperature for carbon and graphitic materials including C/C composites [3,4]. Therefore, to clarify the origin of these features is a very urgent and important issue to C/C composites.

For carbon materials, in general, condition of heat treatment is well recognized to be quite important on their properties. However, there have been a few systematic studies on carbon materials including C/C composites [5-7]. In our studies of unidirectional (UD) C/C composites, the positive temperature dependence of Young's modulus gradually decreases to null and turns to negative with increasing heat treatment temperature (HTT) of C/C composites

[7]. But there is no clear understanding of a correlation between temperature dependence of Young's modulus and microstructure of carbon fibers in C/C composites. Thus, the objective of this research is to present graphitization effects of carbon fibers on temperature dependence of Young's modulus of C/C composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials used were two kinds of UD-C/C composites. Two types of mesophase pitch-based carbon fibers (*F2473* & *F2773*) from the same precursor shown in Table 1 were employed as reinforcement, and the mixture of green coke and phenolic resin (80/20 in volumetric ratio) was employed as matrix precursor. Six types of heat treatments were performed for each two kinds of C/C composites at the carbonized or graphitized temperature, shown in Table 2, for 3.6 ksec in Ar gas. The characteristics of materials used are shown in Table 2. The specimens for Young's modulus measurement with the specimen dimensions of 1 mm in thickness, 5 mm in width and 80 mm in length were cut out aligned to the fiber direction parallel to the longitudinal axis of the specimen.

Table 1 Characteristics of the carbon fibers used.

Fiber Type	Diameter (mm)	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	HTT (K)
<i>F2473</i>	9.8	2.92	542	2473
<i>F2773</i>	9.7	3.28	699	2773

Table 2 Characteristics of the UD-C/C composites used.

<i>F2473</i>			<i>F2773</i>		
HTT (K)	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)	Density ($\times 10^{-3}$ kg/m ³)	HTT (K)	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)	Density ($\times 10^{-3}$ kg/m ³)
1473	45.2	1.62	1473	44.9	1.58
1673	45.1	1.68	1873	42.4	1.68
1873	45.0	1.68	2273	42.7	1.74
2073	45.9	1.71	2473	44.6	1.73
2273	46.6	1.71	2773	43.7	1.76
2773	48.9	1.82	3073	44.1	1.77

Young's modulus measurement was carried out utilizing the recently developed lateral vibration type Young's modulus and internal friction measurement apparatus by electrostatic capacitance method with an advanced high temperature capability and clean vacuum [8]. Young's moduli of C/C composites were determined from resonant frequency under lateral vibration with an strain amplitude about 10^{-5} . The temperature range for this measurement was from 298 K (room temperature ; RT) to 1373 K and a vacuum quality at RT was 2×10^{-5} Pa.

Macroscopic structure, including fiber volume fraction, was determined by both optical and scanning electron microscopies. And microstructural examinations were performed with X-ray diffraction analysis.

RESULTS

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF YOUNG'S MODULUS

The temperature dependences of normalized Young's modulus change by heat treatment are shown in Fig. 1. For the case of *F2473*, there can be seen positive temperature dependences in specimens with HTT lower than 2273 K, but by the heat treatment at 2773 K, the temperature dependence becomes negative. On the other hand, for the case of *F2773*, there can be seen negative dependences in specimens with HTT upper than 2473 K, and there are turnovers from positive to negative dependence in specimens with HTT lower than 2273 K. These turnovers seem to be transient phenomena from positive to negative. And for the cases of both *F2473* and *F2773*, the positive temperature of Young's modulus gradually decreases to null and turns to negative with increasing HTT.

In comparison between the cases of *F2473* and *F2773*, it is clearly understood that temperature dependence changes of Young's modulus of C/C composites are strongly related with microstructural changes of carbon fibers.

Figure 1 Effect of heat treatment on temperature dependence of normalized Young's modulus.

MICROSTRUCTURE INSPECTION BY X-RAY DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS

To understand the microstructural evolution under high temperature heat treatment, X-ray diffraction analysis was applied to the materials used. With increasing HTT, 002 and 004 peaks of graphite became sharp which suggests the enhancement of graphitization. Fig. 2 is enlarged portion of X-ray diffraction patterns from 40 to 60 of 2θ value. 100 and 101 peaks are seen for the cases of *F2473* with HTT at 2773 K and *F2773* with HTT upper than 2773 K. But for another cases, these are not detectable, where so-called 10 peak from turbostratic structure [9] can be identified.

Figure 2 Effect of heat treatment on X-ray diffraction spectra of UD-C/C composites.

From the fact that the positive temperature dependence of Young's modulus is a typical feature for the case of elasticity controlled by entropy, the cases of the latter maintaining a lot of misalignment of c-axis seem feasible to behave like polymer or rubber. On the contrary, for the negative temperature dependences, microstructure dominated by graphitic structure is rationalized to behave like elasticity controlled by energy.

DISCUSSION

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF YOUNG'S MODULUS

The graphitization of carbon fibers in C/C composites with F2473 heat treated at 1473 K is the lowest of all specimens. On the contrary, that in C/C composites with F2773 heat treated at 3073 K is the highest. Now the normalized Young's modulus change of C/C composites heat treated at HTT on test temperature at T K is defined as follows.

$$\Delta E_i(T_{HTT}) \equiv \frac{E_T - E_{RT}}{E_{RT}} \quad (1)$$

Where i is F24 or F27 and indicates the kind of carbon fiber of F2473 or F2773, respectively. So $\Delta E_{F24}(T_{1473})$ and $\Delta E_{F27}(T_{3073})$ are considered as typical examples for the cases of elasticity controlled by entropy and energy, respectively. Then for all the specimens, it is assumed that the temperature dependences of normalized Young's modulus change ($\Delta E_i(T_{HTT})$) could be written by a liner function of the dependences of those two specimens ($\Delta E_{F24}(T_{1473})$ and $\Delta E_{F27}(T_{3073})$) using parameter X . That is, the following function can be written.

$$\Delta E_T(T_{HTT}) = (1 - X) \cdot \Delta E_{F24}(T_{1473}) + X \cdot \Delta E_{F27}(T_{3073}) \quad (2)$$

As the examples of the temperature dependences of parameter X , typical data of the materials used are shown in Fig. 3. In this figure, the parameter X slightly fluctuates up to 900 K and becomes steady at above 900K. So the average values of parameter X at higher than 900 K ($\bar{X}_{T>900}$) are plotted as a function of HTT and are presented in Fig. 4. In this figure, $\bar{X}_{T>900}$ steeply increases with increasing HTT followed to a small amount of increase. The starting point of the steep increase corresponds with the temperature about 400 K under the HTT of their carbon fibers. From the nature of the $\bar{X}_{T>900}$ values, they are supposed to present the microstructural change of carbon fibers in C/C composites. So far, the good coincidence between the HTT dependence of $\bar{X}_{T>900}$ and the temperature dependence change of Young's modulus may support or positive to the concept. Thus, the microstructural changes of carbon fibers in C/C composites seem to start from the temperature about 400 K below the HTT of fibers. This results lead us to consider microstructural stability throughout the manufacturing processes of carbon fibers and C/C composites.

Figure 3 Effect of heat treatment on temperature dependence of parameter X.

Figure 4 Dependence of parameter $\bar{X}_{T>900}$ on heat treatment temperature in UD-C/C composites.

MICROSTRUCTURAL STABILITY OF CARBON FIBER

In the manufacturing process of carbon fibers, carbon fibers are heat treated at HTT for only 30 sec. But in the manufacturing process of C/C composites, C/C composites including carbon fibers are heat treated at HTT for 3.6 msec. So, the microstructure of carbon fibers in C/C composites could be suffered from the thermal history during the process.

The diffusion distance of carbon at T K for t sec, $\bar{z}(t, T)$, is written as;

$$\bar{z}(t, T) = \sqrt{t \cdot D_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{H}{R \cdot T}\right)} \tag{3}$$

Where D_0 , H and R are diffusion coefficient of carbon in carbon fibers, activation energy for diffusion of carbon and gas constant, respectively. Under the condition that $\bar{z}(t_1, T_1) = \bar{z}(t_2, T_2)$, the following relations can be derived.

$$\sqrt{t_1 \cdot D_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{H}{R \cdot T_1}\right)} = \sqrt{t_2 \cdot D_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{H}{R \cdot T_2}\right)} \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{t_1}{t_2} = \exp\left[-\frac{H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1}\right)\right] \tag{5}$$

The Eqn (5) provides the ratio of diffusion time, t_1 / t_2 , to give the same diffusion distance at T_1 and T_2 which correspond to the HTT of carbon fibers and the HTT of C/C composites.

Table 3 shows the t_2 - T_2 relations which satisfy the Eqn (5) under the condition of $t_1 = 30$ sec, $T_1 = 2473$ K or 2773 K. Where the value of H used is 900 kJ/mol [10]. In this calculation, t_1 - T_1 relation is representing the condition of heat treatment of fibers. Therefore, t_2 shorter than 3.6 msec, which is the time period of C/C manufacturing process, indicates that microstructural changes should be taken into account. From this table, $T_2 \geq 2273$ K and $T_2 \geq 2473$ K should include microstructural changes of fibers in C/C composites for the case of $F2473$ and $F2773$, respectively. So, this temperature can be directly connected with results about the HTT dependences of $\bar{X}_{T>900}$. That is, the HTT dependence of $\bar{X}_{T>900}$ would be a good index to indicate microstructural change of carbon fibers in C/C composites.

Table 3 The thermal effect of carbon fibers in C/C composites in the manufacturing process of C/C composites. ($t_1 = 30$ sec, $H = 900$ kJ/mol)

$F2473 (T_1 = 2473 \text{ K})$		$F2773 (T_1 = 2773 \text{ K})$	
T_2 (K)	t_2 (sec.)	T_2 (K)	t_2 (sec.)
1473	2.42×10^{14}	1473	2.75×10^{16}
1673	3.69×10^{10}	1873	4.20×10^9
1873	3.69×10^7	2273	1.61×10^5
2073	1.40×10^5	2473	3.41×10^3
2273	1.40×10^3	2773	3.00×10^1
2773	2.63×10^{-1}	3073	6.64×10^{-1}

CONCLUSIONS

As one of the most important basic mechanical properties of advanced C/C composites for high temperature structural applications, temperature dependences of Young's modulus were precisely studied in a vacuum with a lateral vibration method from room temperature up to 1373 K. The conclusions can be summarized as follows.

- (1) The positive temperature dependence of Young's modulus gradually decreases to null and turns to negative with increasing HTT. And the temperature dependence changes of Young's modulus of C/C composites seem to be strongly related with microstructural changes of carbon fibers in C/C composites.
- (2) From X-ray diffraction analysis, the positive and negative temperature dependences of Young's modulus are considered to be the phenomena like elasticity controlled by entropy and energy, respectively.
- (3) The graphitization of carbon fibers in C/C composites with F2473 heat treated at 1473 K is the lowest of all specimens. On the contrary, that in C/C composites with F2773 heat treated at 3073 K is the highest. For all the specimens, the temperature dependences of normalized Young's modulus can be written by a linear function of the dependences of those two specimens using parameter X .
- (4) The average value of parameter X at higher than 900 K ($\bar{X}_{T>900}$) steeply increases with increasing HTT followed to a small amount of increase. The starting point of the steep increase corresponds with the temperature about 400 K under the HTT of carbon fibers.
- (5) From the thermal history during the manufacturing processes of carbon fibers and C/C composites, the microstructural changes of carbon fibers in C/C composites seem to start from the temperature about 400 K below the HTT of fibers. Thus, the HTT dependences of $\bar{X}_{T>900}$ would be a good index to indicate microstructural change of carbon fibers in C/C composites.

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